

MEDICAL SCIENCES

EXTRAGENITAL PATHOLOGY AND CLINICAL SYMPTOMS IN MEN WITH PATHOSPERMIA

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7528478>

Abstract

The most difficult form of male infertility to treat is azoospermia. Azoospermia is defined as the complete absence of spermatozoa in the ejaculate. The age of the patients who underwent clinical and diagnostic studies varied between 22 and 45 years. Among 119 examined patients with azoospermia, 69 (58.0%) were diagnosed with secretory infertility. In 50 (42.0%) patients, the presence of spermatogenesis in excretory-obstructive infertility was established. Among 69 patients with secretory infertility, 23 had azoospermia in the absence of spermatozoa and spermatogenic cells, which accounted for 33.3% of all patients with secretory infertility (in particular, 2 with leukocytospermia, which indicated damage to the tubular apparatus as a result of previous orchitis). In 46 (66.6%) patients, azoospermia was observed in the absence of spermatozoa, but in the presence of precursor cells of spermatogenesis. Eight (11.6%) patients out of 69 (group 1) were diagnosed with concomitant diseases. We see that arterial hypertension, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, liver, and kidneys occur. Hereditary diseases were not detected in the examined patients. One (4.3%) patient suffered from viral orchitis, one (4.3%) had an operation for phlegmon of the peritesticular, three (13.0%) suffered from non-viral epididymitis, four underwent bilateral orchiectomy at an early age. Pain of varying intensity was found in 6.7% of patients, varying degrees of testicular hypoplasia were found in 7.6%, dysuria in 13.4%, epididymitis in history - 8.4%; history of epidemic mumps - 6.7; 12.6% had depression, restlessness, sleep disorders, and 21.0% had erectile dysfunction. According to clinical examination and ultrasound, chronic prostatitis is suspected in 19.2% of patients. An increase in the number of leukocytes in the blood was found in 15 (13.2%) patients.

Keywords: infertility, azoospermia, genitalia, extragenital pathology, clinical symptoms.

Introduction. In recent years, a progressive increase in cases of male infertility has been recorded in Ukraine and all over the world [1, 2]. The most difficult form of male infertility to treat is azoospermia. Azoospermia is defined as the complete absence of spermatozoa in the ejaculate. Depending on the nature and causes of impaired spermatogenesis, azoospermia is divided into obstructive (excretory, OA) and non-obstructive (secretory, NOA) [1-5]. In male infertility, azoospermia is detected in 10-15% of cases, while the share of obstructive and non-obstructive forms is approximately 40 and 60%, respectively [2-4]. The problem is the differential diagnosis of OA and NOA. OA occurs as a result of secondary obstruction of the male reproductive tract. It is determined on the basis of a comprehensive study of the anamnesis, physical methods, laboratory diagnostic tests, as well as ultrasound and genetic research methods, and histological examination of testicular biopsies. NOA, which develops against the background of primary or secondary damage to the testicular parenchyma, is differentiated from OA based on such features as the consistency and vol-

ume of the testicles, hormone levels, microscopic examination of testicular biopsies, genetic studies (karyotype, microdeletions of the Y-chromosome). Treatment of OA is based on surgical restoration of the patency of the vas deferens, or extraction. However, at present, the most reliable method of diagnosing azoospermia is a testicular biopsy. It allows not only to differentiate excretory and secretory forms of infertility, but also to determine the degree of impaired spermatogenesis based on the histological picture of the biopsy [6-11]. Since obtaining biopsies is a complex and traumatic process, there is an active search for biochemical, genetic, immune markers of azoospermia and expansion of the spectrum of clinical indicators.

Based on this, the aim of the work was the clinical characteristics of patients with various forms of azoospermia.

Materials and Methods. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were taken into account when selecting the research groups.

Inclusion criteria: reproductive age of patients (22-45 years), established fact of infertility, absence of

female infertility factor in marriage, normal testosterone level, absence of acute and chronic infectious-inflammatory processes in the urogenital tract, absence of hormonal correction of infertility.

Exclusion criteria: age < 22 years and > 45 years, severe general systemic diseases, diseases that require taking drugs capable of affecting spermatogenesis, in particular hormonal drugs, varicocele, presence of spermatozoa in the ejaculate, sexually transmitted infections in the anamnesis, presence in history of previously performed testicular biopsy.

The criteria for azoospermia are the absence of sperm in the ejaculate or the absence of ejaculate.

The criteria for the obstructive form of azoospermia are the absence of spermatozoa in the ejaculate with preserved spermatogenesis.

The criteria for non-obstructive form of azoospermia is the absence of sperm in the ejaculate due to a violation of the process of spermatogenesis.

Diagnosis of infertility, like other diseases, is based on the patient's complaints, anamnesis data, objective status and the results of special research methods. It is known that men with infertility, especially with azoospermia, belong to a difficult category of patients, due to the difficulty of diagnosing the causes and degree of impaired spermatogenesis, as well as the choice of treatment methods.

Before the ultrasound examination with dopplerography and elastography, the following tests were performed on all patients: spermogram, blood hormones - FSH, LH, total testosterone, prolactin, estradiol, inhibin B.

Ultrasound with the help of color Doppler mapping and doppleography was used to determine the volume of the testicles and hemodynamic changes in the parenchyma. The research was carried out on a Logiq 3 device from General Electric (USA).

The state of the seminal vesicles, prostate, sonography and dopplerography of the organs of the vestibule-appendages of the testicles, vessels of the vestibule were performed with the help of ultrasound examinations [12]. So, normally, the testicle has an oval shape, a clear and even contour, homogeneous parenchyma, average echogenicity. The protein shell is visualized as a thin continuous strip of high echogenicity located along the edge of the testicle. The mediastinum has the appearance of a hyperechoic thin strip or wedge in the upper parts of the organ. A protrusion with a diameter of 2-3 mm can be visualized at the upper pole of the testicle. The testicle is surrounded by a small amount of serous fluid, which appears as a thin hypoechoic zone 1-3 mm wide. The epididymis is located at the upper pole of the back surface of the testicle. Its structure is heterogeneous and in terms of echogenicity, it is similar to the testicular parenchyma. In the absence of pathological changes in the appendix, only its head, measuring 10-15 mm, is determined. When diagnosing forms of azoospermia, it is important to assess the size and structure of the testicles, the presence of signs of obstruction (dilation of the ducts of the testicle and epididymis), and blood reflux.

Results. The age of the patients who underwent clinical diagnostic tests and testicular biopsy varied between 22 and 45 years. The average age of patients with testicular (secretory) male infertility was 28.6 years, and with posttesticular (excretory) – 31.5 years (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Average age of patients.

The average period of infertility was 4.2 years. This testifies to the patient's long journey to the specialist doctor and his likely unjustified treatment at the polyclinic level without a clearly established diagnosis.

Among 119 examined patients with azoospermia, 69 (58.24 %) were diagnosed with secretory infertility. In 50 (41.76 %) patients, the presence of spermatogenesis in excretory-obturation infertility was ascertained (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Number of patients with azoospermia.

Among 69 patients with a secretory form of infertility, 23 were found to have azoospermia in the absence of spermatozoa and spermatogenic cells, which accounted for 34.0 % of all patients with secretory infertility (in particular, 2 with leukocytospermia, which

indicated damage to the tubular apparatus as a result of previous orchitis) (Fig. 3). In 46 (66.0 %) patients, azoospermia was observed in the absence of spermatozoa, but in the presence of precursor cells of spermatogenesis.

Fig. 3. Distribution of patients with the secretory form of non-obstructive azoospermia

Eight (11.6%) patients out of 69 (group 1) were diagnosed with concomitant diseases (Table 1). We see

that arterial hypertension, diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, liver, and kidneys occur. Hereditary diseases were not detected in the examined patients.

Table 1

Frequency of extragenital pathology in examined patients with non-obstructive form of azoospermia

Concomitant diseases	Number of patients	
	abs.	% of all patients
Chronic gastritis, stomach ulcer	2	2,9
Chronic pyelonephritis	1	1,4
Liver disease	1	1,4
Arterial hypertension	4	5,8

One (4.3%) patient suffered from viral orchitis, one (4.3%) had an operation for phlegmon of the portucallis, three (13.0%) suffered from non-viral epididymitis, four underwent bilateral orchopexy at an early age. According to clinical examination and ultrasound, chronic prostatitis is suspected in 19.2% of patients. An increase in the number of leukocytes in the blood was found in 15 (13.2%) patients.

Table 2

Frequency of clinical symptoms in all examined patients

Clinical symptoms	Number of patients	
	abs.	%
Pain of varying intensity in the area of the external genitalia	8	6,7
Testicular hypoplasia	9	7,6
Epididymitis in the anamnesis	10	8,4
Epidemic mumps in the anamnesis	8	6,7
Dysuria in history	16	13,4
Depressive state, restlessness, sleep disorders	15	12,6
Erectile dysfunction	25	21,0

According to ultrasound, 44 (95.7%) patients with normozoospermia had normal testicle sizes. In 72 (60.5%) patients with azoospermia, the size of the testicles was normal, and in 47 (39.5%) they were reduced.

CONCLUSIONS

1. It was shown that among the patients examined by us, 58.0% were diagnosed with a non-obstructive form of azoospermia, and 42.0% with an obstructive form. According to ultrasound, the volume of the testicles in patients with azoospermia was on average 1.3 times smaller than in patients with normozoospermia.

2. Among the extragenital pathologies, the most frequent cases of the examined patients with non-obstructive form of azoospermia were arterial hypertension and chronic gastritis.

3. The most common clinical symptoms in the examined patients were erectile dysfunction, dysuria, depressive states, and epididymitis.

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